

Ethnobotanical Survey of Endangered Antimalarial and Analgesic Plants of Togo for the Safeguard of the Medicinal Biodiversity

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Authors' contributions

This work was carried out in collaboration between all authors. Authors K. Koudouvo, AD, K. Esseh, K. Essien, and DD designed the study, wrote the protocol and wrote the first draft of the manuscript.

Authors RS, K. Kokou, SKT, KA, JCA and MG, managed the literature searches, analyses of the study performed the structural equation modelling and discuss the conclusion. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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ABSTRACT

The correlation between the threat of species and the use of medicinal plants is necessary for the preservation of this biodiversity. However, in Sub-Saharan Africa, particularly in Togo, where the majority of the population use herbal medicines as first health care recourse, few actions are undertaken to make available the medicinal plants. This study aims for the identification of

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endangered antimalarial and analgesic medicinal plants. Ethnobotanical surveys were realized with Togolese traditional medicine practitioners of Maritime and Lomé-Commune Health Regions. Semi structured interview, "Achat en Triplet de Recettes médicinales" (ATRM) and meetings in focus groups, were methods used for data collection. Parts used, socio-economic data and the phytogeography of the plants, were combined for the identification of the endangerment of medicinal plants.

One hundred and twenty five practitioners have participated to the survey. Between them 31 (44 year age average) have recorded 16 medicinal plants identified by the study as endangered species. These plants belong to 12 families. Leguminosae and Rubiaceae were the most represented families where *Pavetta corymbosa* (27,73%) *Cola millenii* (13,48%), *Uvaria chamae* (13,13%) and *Lannea kerstingii* (11,43%) were the most cited species. Trees (56,25%) were the main biological form living mostly in Perturbed forests (62,50%) and in Savannah (56,29%). Stem bark (34,78%), leaves (26,08%), roots and seeds (17,39% each) and fruits (4,35%) are parts used. *Alstonia boonei* (0.0072 USD/gram of dry Stem bark) was the most expensive plant. The harvest of stem bark and roots (52,17% of part used), combined with the ecology of the plants and the price by gram illustrate the reality of the endangerment of the medicinal plants. *Cola millenii*, *Pavetta corymbosa*, *Dodonea viscosa*, *Senna alata*, *Opillia amantacea*, *Uvaria chamae*, were retained to be cultivated for local needs, where *Alstonia boonei*, *Griffonia simplicifolia* and *Lannea kerstingii*, were selected for regional and international agribusiness.

Keywords: *Ethnobotanical survey; antimalarial plants; analgesic plants; biodiversity endangerment; Togo.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Plants have been used since long time by human to satisfy a variety of needs among with accommodation, furniture, household energy, craft jobs and health care. The last need, requiring medicinal plants [1,2], became an imperative in primary health care of people in poor countries especially those in south Saharan Africa. With the rapid growth of the population, the insecurity and the increasing of people's vulnerability along the years, these peoples have a drastic human pressure on medicinal biodiversity. The consequence of this situation is the endangerment of medicinal plants. In addition, effects of climate change constitute a serious factor of threat of the medicinal plants. These plants become so rare every year. Traditional medicine practitioners in general, particularly herbalists and traditional healers, using medicinal plants as raw material for herbal medicines, became the main actors of this threat. Although these plants are becoming rare and very difficult to get by the practitioners, no action has been taken by them for the protection and conservation of medicinal plants. Also, the local and international needs of medicinal plants are growing. In Togo, there are very few works was addressed to the issue [3]. It is in this context that the CERFOPLAM (Centre de Recherche et de Formation sur les Plantes Médicinales) of University of Lome started a doctoral program linking Sciences, Environment

and Health, an innovation by integrating, the three domains of natural product's research. During studies focused on antimalarial and analgesic plants of Togo [4,5], plants endangered are addressed. Some of these plants will be selected for cultivation to be available for local needs and for agribusiness improvement.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Area of Study

Two Togolese Health Regions: Maritime and Lomé-Commune, constituted the area of study (Fig. 1). These regions represent the ecological zone V with an area of 6100 km², extending between 1° 20' to 1° 50' west longitude and 6° 10' south latitude To 6° 60' north latitude [4,5]. This area is limited at the South part by Atlantic Ocean, the East and the West respectively by Benin Republic and Republic of Ghana. The Health Region of Plateau boards the North of this area. Two rain seasons, a long from March to July and a short from September to November with respectively 1200 mm and 1000 mm for maximal precipitations, 184.4 mm and 66.9 mm for minimal precipitations, characterize the sub-equatorial climate of this area [4,5]. Ewe, Ouatchi, Mina, Fon and Adja are the main ethnic groups of the area [4,6] comprising 2,599,955 people [7].

2.2 Data Collection

The ATRM (Achat en Triplet de Recettes Médicinales) method [5], the semi-structured interview based on a survey questionnaire and meetings in focus groups [8-11], were used for data collection. Market herbalists and traditional healers of Maritime and Lomé-Commune Health Regions of Togo have participated to the survey.

The ATRM particularly involves visiting market herbalists three times separated by one week, to buy recipes of plants used in the treatment of malaria and its related pain. The three successive visits to the markets of sale (MS) are to buy medicinal plant recipes respectively in large number (LN), reduced number (RN) and much reduced number (MR) or single plant (SP). The process is to attend issue of the smallest number of plants in recipes for management of malaria and pain by the same practitioner.

Traditional healers were visited for applying a questionnaire for semi structured interview. They will have to feel the questionnaire with the help of the researcher or students [8,9,11]. Ethnopharmacological data of samples used for malarial and pain were recorded.

Traditional leaders were met in focus group [5] to collect plants and practices used to manage malarial and pain. Leaders of traditional medicine

practitioners and traditional Chefs of each village have contributed as facilitator to the meetings. Here also the ethnopharmacological characteristics of plants were noted.

With the three methods data were recorded on:

- Socio-economic profile of informants like age, sex, ethnic group, instruction level, sources of training and professional experience in traditional medicine
- Plants botany including Latin names, family, local names, biological form and habitat
- Ethno-pharmacology of plant recipes involving used parts, mode of preparation and routes of administration
- Trading characteristics especially with ATRM method like recipes weight, price and physical nature (fresh or dry) on the stalls.

2.3 Data Analysis

Botanical identification of species collected was performed according to the Angiosperms Phylogeny Group classification [12] and the Analytical Flora of Benin [13]. Confirmation of Latin names was conducted by Pr. K. Akpagana. The local names were verified through previous ethnobotanical surveys [4,5]. Statistical processing (SPSS 8.0) and MS Excel spread sheet were used for calculating

Fig.1. Studied area: Maritime and Lomé-Commune Health Regions of Togo

the frequencies of the plants. Biological forms, combined with plant's ecology and with market transactions, were used to evaluate vulnerability and endangerment characteristics of the plants.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Socio-economic Profile of Informants

In the two health Regions of Togo, informants enrolled were 125 practitioners between whom only 31 (12 women and 19 men) have cited 16 endangered species of the total 189 medicinal

plants recorded. Socio-economic characteristics of the informants are presented in Table 1. Informants citing the endangered plants were identified in five ethnic groups, the oldest has 72 years, the youngest 28 years, with an average of 44 years. A few of them has attend school and has practices of traditional medicine as a heritage. Professional experience is from 5 to 41 years of practice of traditional medicine. The average of age indicated that traditional medicine practitioners of Togo are very old. Denou [5] has noted this age characteristic and these usages can be source of endangerment.

Table 1. Informants socio-economic profiles

Code of Informants	Ethnic group	Age (Years)	Sex (Male: M, Female: F)	Levels of instruction	Sources of training	Professional experience (Num. years)
A1	Ewe	44	M	None	Family	20
A2	Ewe	60	M	None	Family	33
A3	Ewe	31	M	Primary, Level 4	Family	07
A4	Ewe	30	F	None	Own self	10
A5	Ewe	40	M	None	Family	15
A6	Ewe	72	F	None	Family	42
A7	Ewe	36	M	Bachelor	School	06
A8	Ewe	53	M	None	Family	21
A9	Ewe	39	F	None	Family	11
A10	Ewe	48	M	Primary, Level5	Family	12
B1	Ouatchi	33	M	Primary, Level 3	School	09
B2	Ouatchi	37	M	None	Own self	10
B3	Ouatchi	28	M	Grammar School 2	Family	05
B4	Ouatchi	61	F	None	Family	38
B5	Ouatchi	40	F	Bachelor	Family	12
B6	Ouatchi	59	M	None	Own self	19
B7	Ouatchi	40	F	None	Family	15
B8	Ouatchi	33	F	None	Family	13
C1	Adja	41	F	Primary, Level 5	Family	21
C2	Adja	28	M	None	Family	07
C3	Adja	44	M	None	Own self	16
C4	Adja	55	M	None	Family	14
C5	Adja	34	M	Bachelor	School	08
C6	Adja	70	M	None	Family	29
D1	Mina	40	F	None	Family	13
D2	Mina	57	M	Bachelor	Own self	22
D3	Mina	39	F	Primary 5	Family	15
D4	Mina	54	M	None	Family	18
E1	Fon	36	M	None	Family	20
E2	Fon	60	F	None	Family	41
E3	Fon	34	M	Primary, Level 3	Family	16

3.2 Recoded Floristic Data of the Plants

The biological forms of the plants (Table 2) were tree (56.25%), liana (18.75%), herb and shrub (12.50% each). Previous studies had identified that trees was the dominant form for plants surveyed [6,14]. Perturbed forests (10 species), savannah (9 species), both (8 species), non-disturbed forests (3species), home garden (2 species) and sea border (one specie) were

endangered plant's habitats. Plants growing in forest were identified by Kokou et al. [6] as dominant ecology of medicinal plants and living in perturbed forest contribute to the treat of medicinal plants [3,6]. The endangered plants belong to 11 families. Leguminosae with 5 species was the most cited family; Rubiaceae was the family of the most frequent specie (Table 2). The two families were cited as dominant in previous studies [15,16].

Table 2. Floristic characteristics of the plants

Latin names	Families	Local names	Citations (%)	Forms	Habitat recorded
<i>Alstonia boonei</i> De Wild.	Apocynaceae	Nyamidua, Ton-Ton, Siaketekre	2.53	Tree	Perturbed forests
<i>Cola millenii</i> . Schum. K	Malvaceae	Assiviatoe, Kpando, Kessedui	15.19	Tree	Perturbed forests/Savannah
<i>Dodonea viscosa</i> F.N. (Jack)	Sapindaceae	Apoufflo, Apoufflotsi	1.26	Herb	Sea border
<i>Griffonia simplicifolia</i> (Vahl. Ex DC) Baill.	Leguminosae	Kpolokou, Kpolouti, Egbodouti	1.26	Liana	Perturbed forests/Savannah
<i>Khaya gradifoliola</i> C.DC	Meliaceae	Mahogen, Mahugen, Mahogani	1.26	Tree	Non-disturbed forests
<i>Lannea kerstingii</i> A. Rich.	Anacardiaceae	Melonku, Melankou, Molonkou	12.65	Tree	Perturbed forests/Savannah
<i>Opilia amantacea</i> Roxb.	Opiliaceae	Kaxe, Kessedoui, Fiodudoami	5.06	Liana	Non-disturbed forests
<i>Parkia biglobosa</i> (Jacq.) Benth.	Leguminosae	Wotsi, Ewoti, Ewati	1.26	Tree	Non-disturbed Forests Savannah /
<i>Pavetta corymbosa</i> (DC.) F. N. Williams	Rubiaceae	Sifafa, Siafa, Siafati	26.56	Shrub	Savannah / Home garden
<i>Pteleopsis suberosa</i> Engl. & Diels.	Combretaceae	Kotokolikan, Sissinon, Akliti	2.53	Tree	Perturbed forests
<i>Sansevieria liberica</i> Hort. ex Gérôme & Labroy	Dracaenaceae	Yoboo, Yodobou, Yodobo	10.12	Herb	Perturbed forests/Savannah
<i>Senna alata</i> L Roxb.	Leguminosae	Madonsohome, Donsoxome	2.53	Shrub	Home garden
<i>Senna sieberiana</i> DC.	Leguminosae	Gati-Gati, Gati, Gatiké	1.26	Tree	Perturbed forests/Savannah
<i>Spathodea campanulata</i> P. Beauv.	Bignonaceae	Adatigolo, Adatsigo, Adassigolo	2.53	Tree	Perturbed forests/Savannah
<i>Uvaria chamae</i> P. Beauv	Annonaceae	Agbanlan, Agbanan, Venavigbe	13.92	Liana	Perturbed forests
<i>Tamarindus indica</i> Linn.	Leguminosae	Atikessigbe, Kététiya, Tamarin	1.26	Tree	Perturbed forests

3.3 Plant's ethnopharmacology

The usage of plant's organs, their mode of preparation and routes of administration were related to each ethnic group with significant variations (Table 3). Stem bark (8 citations), leaves (7 citations), fruit and roots (3 citations each), seeds (2 citations) and bulb (one citation) were plant's parts used. The same used parts were recorded by previous studies in the same area [4,5]. The usage of stem bark and roots (Figs. 2 and 3) concerning 10 plants of the 16 endangered species, is the first illustration of the threat. In Togo only studies of Kokou [3,6] have related the threat of medicinal plants. Wondimu et al. [16] have confirmed the same results. Plants were prepared by decoction (70%), infusion (15%), maceration (10%) and oil extraction (5%). Oral route (100%) was the essential voice of administrated; body bath and unction were cited one time. Recent study [5] has related the similar proportions. *Pavetta*

corymbosa *Sansevieria liberica*, *Uvaria chamae* were cited by all the ethnic groups when *Dodonea viscosa* was cited by only one ethnic group. *D. viscosa*, a plant of sea border is really endangered because of climate change and the destroying of its habitat due to the progressing of the sea on the coastal ground of Togo. Studies realised previously reveal the necessity of the safeguard of this specie [17]. In other West Africa ethnic groups, *U. chamae* and *Parkia biglobosa* were used for craft making and/or construction. This is an important factor for endangerment of medicinal plant [2].

3.4 Price Transactions in Markets

Price of different parts of the plants per kilogram (Table 4) indicated generally, the expansibility the endangered plants. The dry stem bark *Alstonia boonei* (7.5 USD/kilogram) and of *Opilia amantacea* (5.6 USD/kilogram) was the most expansive plant material in the markets.

Table 3. Ethno-pharmacology of the plants

Latin names	Parts used	Modes of preparation	Routes of administration	Informants ethnic groups
<i>Alstonia boonei</i>	Stem bark	Decoction	Oral	A1, A4
<i>Cola millenii</i>	Leaves	Decoction	Oral	A2, A3, A6, A7, A10, B2, B3, B4, B5, C4, C5, D3, D4,
<i>Dodonea viscosa</i>	Seeds	Infusion	Oral	D2
<i>Griffonia simplicifolia</i>	Leaves / Seeds	Decoction/ Oil	Oral/Uction	B8, C1
<i>Khaya gradifoliola</i>	Stem bark	Decoction	Oral	A5, E2
<i>Lannea kerstingii</i>	Stem bark	Decoction	Oral	A1, A2, A3, A8, A9, B3, B5, C2, C3, C4, D2
<i>Opilia amantacea</i>	Leaves/Fruit pulp /Stem bark	Maceration/ Decoction	Body bath/ Oral	A6, A10, B3, , B5, C4, C5,
<i>Parkia biglobosa</i>	Leaves/Roots /Stem bark	Decoction	Oral	A4, C3
<i>Pavetta corymbosa</i>	Leaves	Decoction	Oral	A1, A2, A3, A4, A5, A6, A7, A10, B2, B3, B4, B5, B7, C2, C4, C5, C6, D1, D2, D3, D4, E1, E2, E3
<i>Pteleopsis suberosa</i>	Stem bark	Decoction	Oral	A1, B4, D2
<i>Sansevieria liberica</i>	Bulb	Decoction	Oral	A3, A5, A6, A7, B1, B3, B7, C3, C4, D3, E1
<i>Senna alata</i>	Fruit	Infusion	Oral	B3, C4, E1
<i>Senna sieberiana</i>	Roots	Decoction	Oral	C2, D1
<i>Spathodea campanulata</i>	Stem bark	Decoction	Oral	A3, A7, D4
<i>Uvaria chamae</i>	Leaves/ Roots	Decoction	Oral	A4, A5, A6, A7, A8, A9, B2, B3, B5, C5, D2, D3, E3
<i>Tamarindus indica</i>	Fruit pulp/ Stem bark/ Leaves	Maceration/ Decoction/ Infusion	Oral	D3, B6

The lower price by kilogram was obtained with fresh leaves of *Parkia biglobosa* (0.8 USD/kilogram). Enough biomass of these plants transited every week in the markets (Fig. 4). These prices are too high for people of poor countries living with less than one US dollar by day. During the 10 years of studies for evaluation

of the threat, we noted that prices of medicinal samples increase every year but there are no scientific studies in Togo at the markets (SM or TM) to evaluate this situation. As it was related in other studies, medicinal plants management needs conservation of this biodiversity [14].

Fig. 2 Stem bark *L. kerstingii* in harvesting

Fig. 3 Root of *U. chamae* harvested

Table 4. Trading characteristics of plants

Latin names	Weight (Gram)	Price (USD)	Price/ Kilogram	Plants physical parts used	Physical form
<i>Alstonia boonei</i>	500	3.63	7.2	Stem bark	Dry
<i>Cola millenii</i>	1500	1.82	1.2	Leaves	Fresh
<i>Dodonea viscosa</i>	300	1.2	4.0	Seeds	Dry
<i>Griffonia simplicifolia</i>	800/500	1.0/2.5	1.2/5.0	Leaves / Seeds	Fresh/Dry
<i>Khaya gradifoliola</i>	500	1.5	3.0	Stem bark	Dry
<i>Lanea kerstingii</i>	500	1.8	3.6	Stem bark	Dry
<i>Opilia amantacea</i>	700/300/ 500	2.0/1.5/2.8	2.8/5.0/5.6	Leaves/Fruit pulp /Stem bark	Fresh/Fresh/Dry
<i>Parkia biglobosa</i>	1000/300/500	0.8/1.0/1.0	0.8/3.3/2.0	Leaves/Roots /Stem bark	Fresh/Fresh/Dry
<i>Pavetta corymbosa</i>	500	0.6	1.2	Leaves	Fresh
<i>Pteleopsis suberosa</i>	400	1.4	3.5	Stem bark	Dry
<i>Sansevieria liberica</i>	500	1.0	2.0	Bulb	Fresh
<i>Senna alata</i>	300	1.5	5.0	Fruit	Dry
<i>Senna sieberiana</i>	1200	1.6	1.3	Roots	Fresh
<i>Spathodea campanulata</i>	600	0.6	1.0	Stem bark	Dry
<i>Uvaria chamae</i>	500/300	0.8/0.9	1.6/3.0	Leaves/Roots	Fresh/Dry
<i>Tamarindus indica</i>	800/500/300	1.5/1.2/0.5	1.9/2.4/1.6	Fruit pulp/Stem bark/ Leaves	Dry/Dry/Fresh

Fig. 4. Antimalarial plants harvested

3.5 Selection of Plants for Cultivation and Agribusiness

Six of the 16 threatened species (*Cola millenii*, *Pavetta corymbosa*, *Dodonea viscosa*, *Senna alata*, *Opillia amantacea*, *Uvaria chamae*) were selected for cultivation. In a previous study, only *D. viscosa* was evaluated by biotechnical method for cultivation and adaptation of the specie to a soil different of its sea border soil [14]. National and sub-regional needs (West Africa) of medicinal plants being huge and human pressure on these plants are very strong. Plants cultivation is very important for drugs production [18]. *Alstonia boonei*, *Griffonia simplicifolia* and *Lannea kerstingii*, three trees of forests and savannahs were selected for the agroforestry valorisation. The promotion of agribusiness in Togo from these plants is essential, the international demand for softwood of the stem bark of both *Alstonia boonei*, and *Lannea kerstingii*, and seeds of *Griffonia simplicifolia*, is the motivation. They will be cultivated for agribusiness. The conservation of medicinal plant by indigenous users still a way for safeguard of this biodiversity [19].

4. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This present study has surveyed 16 endangered medicinal plants used in Togo for management of malaria and related pain. This is the first time that a conducted ethnobotanical survey in the country has really addressed the issue. The dominant biological form of the plants (trees), the main parts used (stem bark and roots), the ecological area of the endangered plants (perturbed forests) and the high price per kilogram of the plants have constitute internal and external factors needed to be best managed

for the safeguard of this important biodiversity: Medicinal plants. Six plants selected for cultivation to provide local needs are frequently harvested and sold in many markets. Organs of three other endangered plants: *Alstonia boonei* (stem bark), *Lannea kerstingii* (stem bark), and *Griffonia simplicifolia* (seeds), identified with expansive price per kilogram can be cultivated not only for local usage but also for international agribusiness according to the solicitation of these plants.

Studies will be realised to evaluate comparative chemical active substances in leaves of those plants solicited by stem and/or roots for confirmation of the same component in different organs of a plant. Pharmacological investigations will complete. If leaves of a plant contain the same chemicals and have same or best activities than other organs, sensitisation for good practices of using leaves at the place of stem or root will be undertaken in the benefice of traditional medicine practitioners.

Authors of the present study recommend to traditional medicine practitioners the cultivation of the six selected plants. We recommend also to the police makers (Governments) of our sub-regional countries (West Africa) to provide means for sensitization to good practices in traditional medicine and for planting for agribusiness purpose.

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COMPETING INTERESTS

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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